

Application of Typical Meteorological Years for sizing building integrated PV systems under zero load rejections

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Abstract

Autonomous photovoltaic systems have already been proved as one of the most reliable ways to handle the electrification requirements of remote consumers in isolated areas. The technology improvement in the field of building integrated photovoltaic systems, along with the governmental financial incentives for boosting the corresponding energy sector, have increased the interest of installing small scale photovoltaic systems not only in remote dwellings but also in grid-connected households. The penetration of photovoltaic systems in densely populated areas has made people even more familiar with them and therefore people with environmental consciousness are more likely to adopt the specific technology. In this context, the present work aims in highlighting the capabilities of building integrated photovoltaic systems along with battery storage devices in covering the electrical needs of a typical dwelling using real electricity demand and meteorological data based on Typical Meteorological Year time series. The system is simulated on an hourly basis by using an integrated numerical code that has been developed by the Soft Energy Applications & Environmental Protection Laboratory of the Mechanical Engineering Dept. of Piraeus University of Applied Sciences in Greece. The proposed solution guarantees zero load rejections under different solar potential schemes investigating also the possibilities of minimizing the storage system capacity.

Keywords: RES power; PV systems; BIPV; Building integrated photovoltaic systems

1. Introduction

The photovoltaic (PV) technology has shown a remarkable growth over the last decade. With an annual growth rate reaching 41% for the years 2000 to 2015, PVs are considered as one of the fastest growing market worldwide. Asia and Europe are the top continents in PV installations with 60 and 90 GW respectively [1]. The rate of increment in PV installations is much higher in Asia, and mainly in China, which was ranked as the leading country in PV installations for the year 2015 with more than 40 GW. Europe has also showed increased interest in PV power systems. The year 2013 the installed power of new PV installations was the highest of all the other power plants, even higher from those based on natural gas.

The interest in implementing the PV technology in order to increase the penetration of the renewable energy sources (RES) in the national grid has also been encountered in Greece. Despite the fact that the Greek territory possesses an abundant and reliable solar potential, ranging between 1400-1800 kWh/m² on an annual basis [2], the activity of the PV market was very low at least until the 2010. Since 2010 the installed PV power in Greece has increased more than one order of magnitude. By following the example of other European countries, Greece has also turned to building integrated PV installations, allowing grid-connected households to install PV systems which could feed the local electrical network with PV energy. Despite the recent economic crisis, the installed building integrated PV systems accounted for 21% of the total installed power up to 2014 numbering more than 50,000 of installations [3].

Policy incentives have helped towards the penetration of PVs in densely populated areas affecting positively on public attitude towards PV technology. Given that even more people have become familiar with the environmental degradation issues caused by the use of conventional energy sources, to this end PVs are considered as one of the most likely RES that could extensively penetrate in urban areas either for grid-connected or off-grid installations.

In this respect, the present work aims in highlighting the capabilities of covering the electrical needs of a typical dwelling by using a building integrated PV system along with battery storage devices and the appropriate electronic equipment. Batteries are used for storing excess PV energy in order to cover load demand during periods with low solar radiation or during the night hours so the system can be independent from the local electrical grid. For this purpose, one year of experimental measurements of a typical Greek

household have been implemented along with Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) data series for the areas under investigation. The system's simulation is done on an hourly basis by using the integrated numerical code that has been developed by the Soft Energy Applications & Environmental Protection Laboratory of

Fig. 1. Hourly electricity energy consumption measurements

Fig. 2. Hourly distribution of annual energy demand

the Mechanical Engineering Dept. of Piraeus University of Applied Sciences in Greece [4], [5]. The specific code is applied in order to investigate the possible combinations of PV and storage systems' size which guarantee zero load rejections. The analysis is repeated for different loss of load cases so as to indicate the possibility of minimizing the storage system requirements, which is a major cost for the installation, with lower lifetime than the plant's total.

2. Methodology

The electricity demand profile used for the simulation of the energy balance of a consumer, plays a key role in the sizing procedure of a stand-alone PV-storage system when the restriction parameter is the zero load rejections. Shifting the load from hours with low energy production to hours with high values of solar energy can significantly decrease the system's size and therefore the energy production cost. The utilization of "typical" profiles, although they are considered to be an average expected hourly consumption pattern, most possibly cannot fit to individual cases [4]. Moreover, by investigating consumers who cover their energy needs solely from RES-based systems it has been proved that at the end of the day the consumer adjusts his energy consumption habits to the RES availability. According to the above, the specific work was implemented as case-specific by recording for a year-round the energy demand of a four-member family dwelling with an annual electricity consumption of 4416 kWh (Fig. 1). Although the specific household is located in the greater Athens area, the electrical energy profile can also be considered in different urban areas as it does not include thermal load coverage. The low consumption during August, shown in the graph, is attributed to the summer vacations during which only the base load is necessary.

By investigating the diurnal variation of the annual energy demand (Fig. 2), 70% of the energy is consumed mainly during the morning and evening hours. The maximum energy demand during the night hours was found to be 6.5 kWh which can be considered as the minimum requirements for energy storage capacity.

The specific energy profile demand was simulated in selected areas throughout the Greek region which include major cities in each one of the four Climatic Zone in Greece (Fig. 3). The meteorological data for the corresponding cities have been drawn from an extended (39 areas) TMY database which has been developed on the basis of 15 years of historical meteorological measurements [6]. The TMYs are datasets of hourly values of solar radiation and meteorological parameters which are composed of months selected from individual years, concatenated to form a complete year. The TMY is defined as a year representing climatic conditions considered to be typical over a long period of time and is broadly used in energy systems' simulations.

For the energy balance simulation of the system an integrated algorithm was used, designed in order to produce all system combinations which can guarantee energy load satisfaction based on the selected loss of load hours value and the size limitations requested by the user. Note that system combinations produced

by the algorithm correspond to specific TMY timeseries and a specific load demand profile. The input parameters include: PV panel characteristics, solar radiation values and meteorological data on an hourly time step, necessary components' characteristics and efficiency curves (e.g. inverter, converter, charge controller etc.) and the corresponding load profile also on an hourly basis. It is important to notice that the specific algorithm does not select the components of the configuration under investigation, contrariwise the user selects all the necessary components of the installation and the program estimates the energy performance for every possible combination of the systems' components, based on the investigation limits defined by the user.

After having defined all the components and parameters of the system, the estimation of the appropriate configuration that guarantees the energy autonomy of the consumer is taking place through the following steps:

Fig. 3. Representative locations under investigation

1. Define the number of PV panels to be used taking into consideration the existing solar intensity and the corresponding ambient temperature.
2. Select a battery capacity value taking into account the desired hours of the system energy autonomy.
3. At each time step complete the following steps:
4. At the current time step, estimate the energy produced by the PV station.
5. Check whether the output of the PV generator production branch is greater than the energy demand of the system. If this is true, charge the batteries of the installation with the energy surplus under the condition that the batteries are not full. In the opposite case the energy surplus is forwarded to low-priority loads. Then proceed to the next time step, i.e. step 7.
6. If the energy demand cannot be covered by the PV generator production, the energy deficit is covered by the batteries under the assumption that the batteries are not near the maximum permitted depth of discharge. Otherwise, increase the battery capacity by a given amount and go back to step 3.
7. Proceed to analyse the next time step, steps 4–6, until the entire time period is completed.
8. Increase the PV panel number and repeat steps 2–7.

After the analysis is completed, all combinations of storage system's size and PV power generator are given taking into account that every set of PV and storage system ensures the energy autonomy of the consumer for the entire period analysed.

3. Results

The present analysis is focused on selected representative locations for each Climatic Zone of Greece (Fig. 3). More specifically, autonomous building integrated PVs are investigated at the location of Kastoria and Thessaloniki in Northern Greece, Athens in Central Greece and Heraklion in South Greece. By

applying the above-described model for the four areas under investigation, the results of Fig. 4 are obtained.

Fig. 4. Zero load rejection PV-storage systems

Fig. 5. Hourly energy balance of PV-storage system for 4 consecutive days in January

According to the results, the increase of installed PV power can significantly reduce the required storage capacity with the rate of storage decrease being higher in areas of Northern Greece which possess lower solar potential. For example, in Thessaloniki the increase in installed PV power by 2 kW can reduce the required storage capacity by 40% (from 180 to 120 kWh). The effect of the solar potential to the system size is highly noticed on the minimum storage capacity requirements for satisfying zero load rejections. More precisely, while for providing energy autonomy in the region of Kastoria the installation of 10 kW PV power requires a 120 kWh storage capacity, in Heraklion, for the same PV power, the required storage capacity is reduced by 50%. It is also obvious that increase of the installed PV power higher than the 20 kW does not contribute in storage capacity reduction as the batteries reach their minimum required capacity

Fig. 6. Annual energy balance of the produced PV energy for installed PV power 10 kW

Fig. 7. Annual energy balance of the produced PV energy after minimizing storage capacity

(20 kWh). Taking into consideration the maximum energy consumption during the night hours (6.5 kWh) one can conclude that the minimum storage capacity resulting from analytical simulations is three times higher.

The investigation of the hourly energy balance of the system allows the identification of adverse periods for the batteries, i.e. periods with low solar potential and high energy demand. An example of such situation is presented in Fig. 5 which shows the energy balance for consecutive days of January for an autonomous system comprising of 18 kW installed PV power and 20 kWh storage capacity. According to the graph, at the noon of the 1st day the batteries have reached their maximum storage capacity. In the following days, low solar potential exists and the PV energy production during the daytime cannot fulfill the energy requirements during the night. The energy deficit is covered by the batteries which reach their depth of discharge (DoD) limit at the morning hours 3 days later. Events similar to the above, finally result in tripling the storage capacity compared to the maximum energy needs during the night.

By comparing the solar potential of the areas under investigation with the energy requirements of the

selected consumer, one can easily realize that the PV-storage systems' size that the model proposes is overestimated in order to succeed zero load rejections. The energy excess can reach, in some combinations, even 80% of the produced energy from the PVs (Figs 6 and 7). The energy balance results of Fig. 7 represent installations of 10 kW PV power with the minimum necessary storage capacity for the different areas under investigation. The same energy balance is recalculated for the same PV power combined with increased values of storage capacity (Fig. 6). The two figures indicate that there is a strong relationship between storage capacity and excess energy which can be compensated by the utilization of excess energy to secondary loads e.g. desalination, water pump etc. Another important issue raised from the energy balance charts is the fact that the energy demand is covered by almost 50% through the batteries and the rest is covered directly from the PV panels on a year round operation.

Fig. 8. Effect of loss of load requirements in system sizing

In order to decrease the overall system's size, the possibility of accepting loss of load for up to 100 hours in total during the year is investigated. In Fig. 8 different cases of loss of load are investigated ranging between 0 (zero load rejections) and 100 hours (1.14% of the year) in Kastoria (an area with low solar potential). According to the results, by accepting only 10 hours of loss of load during the year can decrease the storage capacity requirements up to 10 kWh. Using Fig. 8 the user is able to select the combination which, according to the importance of his loads and the cost for being left without electricity per hour, is satisfying his needs.

4. Conclusions

The present work is based on the use of a calculation algorithm in order to highlight the capabilities of the building integrated PV systems along with battery storage devices in covering the electrical needs of dwellings under the restriction of zero load rejections. The model utilizes real electricity demand measurements along with meteorological data based on TMYs in order to define the possible combinations of the system's components which achieve zero load rejections. According to the results, in order to minimize the storage requirements, the installed PV power should be significantly increased and therefore increase the amount of the PV energy that cannot be absorbed. It is also significant to point out that during the system operation, only half of the produced electricity is directly forwarded to the loads and the rest through the storage system which also affects the life expectancy of the batteries.

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